

Towards Enhancing the Media Industry through AI-Driven Image Recommendations

George E. Raptis¹, Vasilis Theodorou¹, and Christina Katsini¹

Human Opsi, Patras, Greece, {graptis,vtheodorou,ckatsini}@humanopsis.com

Abstract. In a fast-changing media ecosystem, professionals and enterprises in the News and Media industry face new challenges that they should address to maximize their productivity and improve their services. The rise of alternative news sources, such as social media, the leading news source, especially for young people, has led to emerging requirements in the News and Media industry. A core requirement is publishing articles as fast as possible on various platforms, combining visual and textual content. Accompanying news with images raises the readers' interest, improves engagement, and recall. Therefore, the News and Media industry professionals must adapt their publication strategies to meet this requirement and the media consumers' expectations. However, the selection of the appropriate images is a time-consuming and manual task. Towards this direction, we propose VIREO, which addresses this challenge by providing professionals (e.g., journalists) with an integrated digital solution that automatically recommends a collection of images that could accompany an article. VIREO implements text and image analysis and matching processes leveraging AI techniques in real time to achieve this. VIREO aims to benefit both professionals (e.g., journalists) by suggesting appealing images that accompany the textual content of their articles and create breath-taking stories and the media consumers (e.g., readers) by delivering an enhanced reading experience, engagement, and recall.

Keywords: Image Recommendation · Artificial Intelligence · Image-to-text Matching · Content Creation · Media Industry · Computer Vision.

1 Introduction

In recent years, the media ecosystem has changed due to emerging technological advances and the rise of social media. It is an increasingly evolving environment with the people working in it (e.g., journalists, content creators, authors, and news professionals) frequently facing new challenges. The rise of alternative news sources (e.g., social media being the primary news source, especially for young audiences) has led to several requirements in the media industry. Among them, a core one is the need for publishing as fast as possible on various platforms combining text and images to reach the target audience. Accompanying news with images that best depict the main content and keywords of the news, raises the readers' interest in the news and improves engagement [5]. Therefore, news

and media industry professionals need to adapt their publication strategies to better meet these requirements and match the media consumers' (e.g., readers') expectations.

Considering that i) several tools that support cross-posting (i.e., sharing the same content across multiple platforms), such as Planable, eClincher, Buffer, and Hootsuite, are available in the market and save time and ii) professionals in the news and media industry have quick access to new information which they can check against fake news, hoaxes, and scams (e.g., eufactcheck.eu, IFCN, Google fact check tools, FactCheck.org), the burden falls into the need for quickly accompanying the article content (text) with related image(s). Therefore, the challenge is to deliver image recommendations based on text to create visually appealing stories and eventually save time for professionals in the news and media industry (e.g., journalists).

To this end, we propose VIREO, with the following objective: develop and evaluate an integrated digital solution to recommend a collection of images that could accompany an article, based on content analysis. The matching and the recommendation are based on applying artificial intelligence (AI) techniques and should be performed in close to real time. The project outcome should benefit both the authors (e.g., journalists) by enabling them to quickly select appealing images and create engaging and appealing stories and the media consumers (e.g., readers) by having an enhanced reading experience, engagement, and recall.

2 Challenges and architecture

Research attempts have highlighted the importance of building tools to summarize news articles into images using AI techniques. Although they follow reliable methods, their performance and maturity level are limited [1, 2, 5, 10]; therefore, there is room for improvement. The most common challenges in such works include the natural language understanding (NLU) to capture text concepts other than general [2, 6, 3] and the accurate image suggestion, focusing on eye-catching visual content that expresses diverse states (e.g., appealing, surprising, polarization, positive/negative) [4, 9, 8]. VIREO aims to overcome these challenges following a validated research framework [4] through a 3-step-and-innovation process: i) developing a mechanism that understands and represents article content in a machine-readable and understandable format, ii) developing a tool that supports accurate image caption embeddings processes, and iii) integration of these tools providing accurate and fast image recommendations.

Hence, VIREO consists of three main components: i) **Article Analysis** component that uses NLP techniques, such as tokenization, part-of-speech tagging, and named entity recognition, to analyze the text and extract relevant information; ii) **Image Analysis** component that uses computer vision techniques, such as feature extraction and image classification, to analyze the images and extract relevant information; iii) **Image Matching and Recommendation** component that uses AI techniques to match the images to the text (based on the extracted information) and recommend a collection of images that could ac-

Fig. 1. The conceptual architecture of VIREO.

company an article. Besides these, VIREO also has the following components: iv) **Data Collection** component that collects and preprocesses the text and image data, such as news articles and images, that will be used to train and test the system; v) **Repository** that stores the data and information used by the system, such as the text, images, and matching results; vi) **User Interface** that provides an interface for the users, such as journalists, to interact with the system and select the recommended images; vii) **Data Privacy and Security** that ensures compliance with data privacy laws and regulations and secure data handling. Fig. 1 depicts the conceptual architecture of VIREO.

Next, we discuss the information flow for each component. For the Article Analysis component, after the author submits their article, the summarization of the article starts with the application of text processing techniques such as TextRank. The result goes through the keyword extraction process, which applies part-of-speech tagging, Lemmatization, Word frequencies, and similar techniques. The word embeddings generation follows, with Pretrained (transformer) models (e.g., BERT, GloVe, Word2Vec). The final step is the generation of MRU subspace vectors. The Image Analysis component follows a similar process. First, the image captions are generated through SAT, CNN, and RNN techniques. Then, the keywords are extracted, and word embeddings are generated along with the vector subspace in line with the processes presented before. This process is executed for all the available images in the collection before the article submission. The results are stored in the repository. Regarding integration, when an author writes an article, the text and image analysis tools run in the background, leading to matching between textual and visual content and, thus, recommending a collection of images that could accompany the article. A recommendation engine aggregates the outcomes of the afore processes. It provides the best-fitting image suggestions based on machine- and deep-learning techniques, such as classification, hierarchical analysis, CNNs, and cosine similarities.

3 Discussion

3.1 Impact on media and AI ecosystems

VIREO potentially impacts the media ecosystem, the broader AI ecosystem, and HCI. Regarding the media ecosystem, its impact may be materialized by improving the efficiency and effectiveness of the content creation process. Using AI to recommend images to accompany articles can help journalists quickly select appealing and relevant images that enhance the story and create a more engaging and memorable reading experience. This can improve the quality of the media content and increase audience engagement and retention. Additionally, automating the image selection process can save journalists time and resources, allowing them to focus on other aspects of their work. This could increase organizations' productivity and ultimately reduce costs. VIREO can also benefit the media industry by providing valuable insights into audience preferences and interests to inform content creation and advertising strategies. Using AI to analyze and match text with images can contribute to personalization, which can be used to create more tailored experiences for readers. Furthermore, by leveraging AI-driven image recommendation, VIREO has the potential to foster innovation in the media industry by enabling the exploration of new storytelling formats and creative approaches that captivate audiences in novel and immersive ways.

Regarding the impact on the broader AI ecosystem, NLP techniques can help improve and advance state of the art in this field. As more and more users use the system, the data collected will help to train and improve the NLP model, leading to better and more accurate results. Computer vision techniques can also improve and advance this field's state of the art. The system's ability to match images to text in real-time will generate more data and insights that can help to improve the understanding of images and improve the computer vision algorithms. Apart from that, VIREO's ability to understand and match images to text in real-time and deliver relevant images to the users will help to improve the understanding of the users' preferences, which can be used to improve the overall AI-human interaction. By providing a new way for media organizations to select images, VIREO can also open up new business models for the media industry (e.g., enable media organizations to create new revenue streams by licensing images, enable media organizations to offer personalized subscription plans or premium content tailored to the consumers' preferences).

3.2 Steps towards evaluation

VIREO could impact HCI, but to fully understand it, we should conduct evaluation studies with media producers (e.g., authors) and media consumers (e.g., readers). For media producers, the evaluation will focus on assessing the usability and usefulness of VIREO in the content creation process. Media producers will be asked to use VIREO to suggest images for their articles and provide feedback on the system's recommendations. They will be asked to evaluate the relevance, appeal, and suitability of the recommended images for their articles.

Media producers' feedback will help identify any shortcomings in the image recommendation process and provide insights into how VIREO can be improved to better meet their needs. Additionally, the evaluation will gather data on time saved by media professionals when using VIREO compared to manual image selection processes, allowing for a quantitative assessment of its efficiency. For media consumers, the evaluation will focus on assessing the impact of VIREO on their reading experience, engagement, and recall. They will be provided with articles with images selected using VIREO and articles without recommended images. They will then be asked to read both versions of the articles and provide feedback on their overall engagement, interest, and recall of the content. Comparative analysis between the two groups will help determine how VIREO enhances the reading experience and captures readers' attention. Additionally, media consumers' feedback on the relevance and appeal of the recommended images will be collected to refine and optimize the image recommendation process further.

The evaluation process will include a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods. We will conduct surveys, interviews, and focus groups to gather qualitative feedback from media producers and consumers. Quantitative measures such as time saved by authors, click-through rates on articles with recommended images, and user engagement metrics will also be collected to provide objective insights into the system's performance and impact. In addition to evaluating the effectiveness and usability of VIREO, security and privacy aspects will be considered during the evaluation process. Advanced techniques like eye-tracking may gather data on users' security and privacy perceptions when interacting with the system [7]. We will implement stringent measures to ensure the privacy and confidentiality of users' data, including anonymization and secure storage protocols.

For the evaluation study, we will obtain user consent and research ethics regulations will be strictly followed to protect participants' rights and ensure a secure evaluation environment. We will take special consideration for managing the copyright of the images and text used by VIREO throughout the design and development process and ensuring compliance with research ethics regulations regarding the participation of adults in user studies. These would provide insights into the usability and user experience of the system and would help identify potential pain points or areas of improvement for the system, as well as provide feedback on the effectiveness of the image-to-text matching and delivery system. Such studies would provide insights into the impact of VIREO on the media industry and potential business opportunities.

Acknowledgments

VIREO has indirectly received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation action programme, via the AI4Media Open Call #2 issued and executed under the AI4Media project (Grant Agreement no. 951911).

References

1. Chu, W.T., Kao, M.C.: Blog article summarization with image-text alignment techniques. In: 2017 IEEE International Symposium on Multimedia (ISM). IEEE (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ism.2017.40>
2. Darimbekov, Z., Ubingazhibov, A., Serikbulatova, Z., Demirci, M.F.: News2Image: Automated system of image recommendation to news articles. In: 2020 IEEE 4th International Conference on Image Processing, Applications and Systems (IPAS). IEEE (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1109/ipas50080.2020.9334931>
3. de-Lima-Santos, M.F., Ceron, W.: Artificial intelligence in news media: Current perceptions and future outlook. *Journalism and Media* **3**(1), 13–26 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.3390/journalmedia3010002>
4. Deldjoo, Y., Schedl, M., Cremonesi, P., Pasi, G.: Recommender systems leveraging multimedia content. *ACM Computing Surveys* **53**(5), 1–38 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3407190>
5. Ha, J.W., Kang, D., Pyo, H., Kim, J.: News2Images: Automatically summarizing news articles into image-based contents via deep learning. In: INRA@ RecSys. pp. 27–32 (2015)
6. Jere, R., Pandey, A., Shaikh, H., Nadgeri, S., Chandankhede, P.: Using machine learning for image recommendation in news articles. In: *Advances in Intelligent Systems and Computing*, pp. 215–225. Springer Singapore (2021). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-3342-3_18
7. Katsini, C., Abdrabou, Y., Raptis, G.E., Khamis, M., Alt, F.: The role of eye gaze in security and privacy applications: Survey and future HCI research directions. In: *Proceedings of the 2020 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*. pp. 1–21. CHI '20, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3313831.3376840>
8. Liu, F., Lebet, R., Orel, D., Sordet, P., Aberer, K.: Upgrading the newsroom. *ACM Transactions on Multimedia Computing, Communications, and Applications* **16**(3), 1–28 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3396520>, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3396520>
9. Mohnish, S.P., Deepak, G., Praveen, S.V., Sheeba Priyadarshini, J.: DKMI: Diversification of web image search using knowledge centric machine intelligence. In: *Knowledge Graphs and Semantic Web*. pp. 163–177. Springer International Publishing (2022). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-21422-6_12
10. Svensson, P.: Automated Image Suggestions for News Articles: An Evaluation of Text and Image Representations in an Image Retrieval System. Master's thesis, Department of Computer and Information Science, Linköping University (2020), <http://urn.kb.se/resolve?urn=urn:nbn:se:liu:diva-166669>